

Data Centre Websites: assessing usability & navigation

Authors:

Jesse Alexander ^{1,2}

Affiliations:

- 1 - NERC Environmental Data Service
- 2 - Science and Technology Facilities Council
- 3 - British Geological Survey

Contents

About this work	3
Summary	3
Rationale for the work	4
Methodology	4
Results	5
Common usability issues	10
Lessons learnt	12
Opportunities and future recommendations	12

About this work

The BOOST EDS project, [funded by UKRI and supported by DSIT](#), aimed to pilot a range of measures to address issues of data findability, traceability, accessibility and interoperability, to improve data sharing and access across disciplines. Conducted from late 2023 to March 2025, the project consisted of five work packages, with one work package dedicated to user centred approaches in the context of environmental data services. The work was undertaken by members of the NERC Environmental Data Service (EDS).

This is a summary report to provide supporting information to the overarching report - User centred approaches for environmental data services: embedding co-creation and collaboration (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15115280>)

Summary

The NERC data centres all have the same goal: to facilitate environmental science by ensuring data is findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable. To achieve this, a clear, intuitive, and navigable website is vital to ensure a smooth user experience when accessing our services. However, there is often a greater focus on adding new tools and important information without examining our sites as a whole to see how they flow and function.

This project involved the systematic assessment of the data centre websites using heuristic evaluations to appraise their usability. The goal was to understand the strengths and weaknesses of each site to learn what recommendations could be made to each data centre for improvements to the user experience of their site. The final aim is to work together across sites to co-create better user services.

Target audience

A key aspect to consider when designing websites and services is the groups of people who visit our site and the goals they have. Since we are mostly unable to ask or identify what a user's aim is when they visit our site, we have to ensure that we have made it simple and easy for them to traverse the site and access the specific service(s) they are looking for.

An effective method of ensuring that we don't forget our users' needs is to create user personas - fictional profiles that represent examples of people our users could be. These personas help us consider what journey different users would take through our site and what they would be looking to achieve when visiting our site.

Below are some examples of different personas that showcase examples of what our users would look like from 4 different sectors: Academia, Public, Industry, and Government.

Name Malachi Dreadson – he/him	Industry Academia	Picture 			
Description Malachi is 24 and has recently graduated with a masters in biological sciences and is starting his PhD looking at how algae is affected by the weather & climate and would like to use data stored on the CEDA Archive. He is being guided by his supervisor but will also need a data management plan from one of the data centres. Most likely CEH or CEDA.			Description Ash is 35 and works as a garden landscaper and wants to understand more about the environment including local flora and fauna, the geology & hydrology of the local area and current & future weather patterns. All of this to help make sure that they can create the best gardens that won't negatively impact the local ecosystem and be resistant to extreme weather events in the future.		
Goals Analyse the effect that local weather has on algae coverage and explore how changes in algae prevalence can be used as climate indicators.	Challenges Has limited atmospheric science knowledge and minimal programming experience. Will need to learn how to find, access and analyse NetCDF data or other similar datatypes.	Context Having never done any sort of atmospheric research before, Malachi will need to learn a lot about weather and climate whilst also getting to grips with the data formats.	Goals Find out about the local soil and earth content and how they should factor this in when planning gardenscapes. Consider future extreme weather events and how to mitigate these.	Challenges Doesn't know how to find data / what data is available. They also struggle with overly technical language and academic publications and would prefer more accessible resources.	Context Ash doesn't have any guidance or suggestions on where to start so is largely self-guided in conducting their research. Will only be looking at data on a very local scale.
Name Serenity Eisenhower – she/her	Category Industry	Picture 			
Description Serenity is 43 and works as an insurance agent. As part of her role, she must evaluate certain insurance claims that could relate to weather, climate, and other environmental factors in order to decide whether this is a valid claim. She must also figure out how much insurance rates would be on different properties such as houses that are at risk from coastal erosion.			Description Jethro is 28 and works for the government advising the minister of state for DEFRA and minister of state for Science, Research and Innovation. He must wrap his head around key scientific topics and current research in order to advise the ministers on current trends and possible concerns in science. They must also help influence policy decisions that will affect the scientific and wider UK landscape.		
Goals Explore previous weather events and correlate those with insurance claims. Use future climate predictions to decide on insurance rates for properties.	Challenges Isn't an environmental scientist and has only a basic understanding of how to examine the climate. Isn't sure how to conflate previous weather events with damages or impacts.	Context Serenity doesn't need to have a full in-depth understanding of our climate but instead just needs to know how it can impact certain buildings and structures and the damages as a result.	Goals Research and understand significant happenings within the scientific community in order to provide up-to-date advice to policy makers in the UK government.	Challenges Is quite short on time and must cover a lot of information in a clear & concise way. Isn't able to conduct his own research but instead needs simple, clear & concise findings readily available.	Context Jethro will be conversing with lots of different individuals, organisations and companies and must pick out key elements to share with people who are higher up the ladder.

In the future when we improve our websites, it's important to keep referring to these personas to make sure that our site is functional for our wide range of users. Without being able to easily ask what our users would like from us, we need to assume a large variety of goals and make each one easily accessible and understandable.

Rationale for the work

As we move towards a unified Environmental Data Service, we want to ensure we deliver a consistent service across data centres. Despite covering different areas of environmental science, the data centres have a similar mission.

Each data centre has unique aspects and features that shine through in their website, they will also have certain parts that don't compare as favourably to the other centres. Evaluating the different sites helps identify their strengths and weaknesses and highlight areas that we can improve through collaboration and evaluation.

Methodology

To assess the websites, we conducted heuristic evaluations of the 5 NERC data centres using Jakob & Nielsen's 10 usability principles. These are some of the most commonly used usability inspection methods and are great at finding roadblocks that prevent users from performing certain tasks. It is a relatively simple and efficient method and is readily available, which is beneficial when looking at

multiple different websites. However, it is an isolated process that is prone to biases and personal preferences and also doesn't involve listening to users' opinions.

A competitor analysis was also conducted on the websites of similar organisations, such as the US Geological Survey. This was done using a SWOT analysis - identifying the strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and threats related to a site. Examining other websites that have similar goals helps us identify where they excel and where there is room for improvement. This allows us to consider what design aspects each site excels at and where there is room for improvement. Below is a summary of the findings for each data centre, and then we have identified the key usability issues across all the sites.

Results

The British Oceanographic Data Centre has a very nice design, with bold and consistent theming. However its visual appeal sometimes comes at an expense. For example, the homepage isn't scaled correctly on most browsers, showcasing an image that cuts off a section of the introductory paragraph. There is also a broken link on the homepage, in the highlighted projects section the Gliders project doesn't have a page and causes a 404 error. Both of these occur on the first page most users visit, leaving a bad impression.

Part of the UK's National Oceanography Centre BODC provide instant access to over 130,000 unique data sets.

As the UK's National Oceanographic Data Centre (NODC) marine data centre within the Natural Environment Research Council's (NERC) Environmental Data Service (EDS), BODC helps provide answers to both local questions such as the likelihood of coastal flooding, or global issues such as the impact of climate change.

Something that this site struggles with is link consistency, most sites and programs that exist all use the [same formatting](#) to indicate that there is a link, this makes it easy for users to identify links no matter where they are online. However, the BODC site has some links that do not function at all and some pieces of text that look like links but aren't in fact.

On the privacy and cookies page none of these 'links' are functional apart from the very last one. They are clickable but do not take you anywhere.

'Microsoft Word' in the example below looks like a link consistent with all the other links on the site, however, it is not one at all, despite changing colour when you hover over it. These examples contradict the user's existing knowledge of online navigation.

[Microsoft Word](#)

- Many downloadable files on this web site are made available as Microsoft Word documents as an alternative to PDF files.
- The documents have been created using Microsoft Word 2002. It is therefore advisable that you ensure you have this version or later installed before downloading.

Privacy and cookies

This covers the British Oceanographic Data Centre's web site to external web sites are not covered by this information.

- [Standard information collected](#)
- [BODC web user accounts](#)
- [Cookies](#)
- [What are cookies?](#)
- [Our use of cookies](#)
- [Essential cookies](#)
- [Performance cookies](#)
- [Preference \(or functionality\) cookies](#)
- [How to control cookies](#)

Overall as a site, BODC does a great job of organising a huge amount of content, possibly the most extensive of all the data centre sites. However, with such a large site, it is a little convoluted with pages grouped under sections, headings, topics, subsections etc. Sometimes pages are linked to multiple times from the sidebar, toolbar or just the text of the page itself. This complicates the structure of the site and can confuse users traversing the site for the first time.

There is a lot of room for the site to be simplified, the [Data Planning](#) page for example has 4 child pages, and each of those pages is no more than a few paragraphs long, meaning that those 5 pages could easily be combined into 1 page just with different sections. There are currently over 120 links just in the toolbar alone! Cutting down or combining certain pages could effectively address this.

The Centre for Environmental Data Analysis has the unique position of being the data centre for two NERC research centres (NCAS & NCEO) and has the most expansive archive. When focusing on just the archive site, there are some issues with the ‘refine search’ options which could severely hinder the search functionality. The options suffer from a lack of explanation or help documentation coupled with confusing icons. The picture on the left shows 3 ‘Datasets options’ which each have a small icon next to each option which do not function at all and are not able to be clicked. The icon next to ‘Bounding box’ does function however it just toggles whether that section is displayed or not - essentially a drop-down box toggle, it doesn’t give any information about the bounding box feature which

one might expect and I had to figure out how it functioned through trial and error since I could not find an explanation anywhere.

Another issue is that the homepage has boxes which are semi-transparent with a detailed background image behind them. Whilst this is still functional, it makes it harder to interpret visually and likely has accessibility issues. This could also be fixed relatively easily.

There are a few other functionality problems I found: Visiting an outdated dataset will alert you that you're currently viewing a dataset that has been superseded and links to the "latest version". However, this isn't the latest version and is just the version that was uploaded the soonest after the one you're viewing, which means you might have to click through 5+ pages to get to the latest version.

The top 3 of CEDA's Special Record Selections also don't return any results and another leads to a 500 error. There is also a button on the catalogue search saying "Tell us what you think" which links to a feedback form. After filling out the form months ago I don't know how often this feedback is acknowledged or listened to, and you are also able to view everyone else's answers to the form.

The Environmental Information Data Centre site is pretty simple, which would be a good thing if there weren't duplicate links, inconsistencies and questionable icon choices. The search functions as intended but when looking to enhance the search using filters or the spatial search option, this causes issues and lacks intuitiveness or just doesn't function at all. The site itself isn't super visually appealing, but I think some small changes would go a long way to improve the look and feel of the site.

For example when choosing how to view a record: I would assume all these options would have the same effect whereas some will download a file and the others will open it in a new tab. Ideally, there would be something to indicate how each option would function, even better would be an explanation of the different data types with suggestions or guidance on how to open and read each one.

For having limited pages and content within the site, the pages are populated with links to other pages that are often duplicated or appear on multiple pages, reducing the site's navigability. There are also multiple broken links in the FAQ section and other parts of the site as well as some convoluted CoreTrustSeal links.

When filtering search results by topic, you click on different topics to toggle whether those results are shown or not, however, there is very little indication to show whether a topic is toggled or not and instead just has a small cross icon. Because of this, it's quite tricky to tell which topics have already been selected.

Another issue is the special search function which I would assume is a way to narrow down a search by selecting an area that the results must include, however, this feature is completely broken and I cannot get it to work at all. There is also no accompanying help documentation or guidance for this feature which adds further complexity.

Overall this site could be hugely improved with relatively minor visual changes that are most consistent with other websites.

The **National Geoscience Data Centre** has an attractive-looking site which makes use of numerous features like drop-down boxes to help organise and simplify content on the site. There is also a wealth of information contained on the site, in part due to the lack of separation between the NGDC and the British Geological Survey website. There are a lot of parent pages with numerous child, grandchild and even great-grandchild pages which means that navigating the site often requires multiple clicks to reach specific pages that aren't always in obvious locations.

Every page also has this header with the option to 'Share this article', which seems counterintuitive when most of the pages couldn't be classed as articles. It also has the old Twitter(X) logo and the opportunity to share on Pinterest which just links to the BGS Pinterest page which isn't used at all and has 6 pins on it.

On this site there are a lot of great features for finding and accessing data including filtering and exportation options and customisable views within the site, however, once the data is downloaded it is up to the user and those without technical skills would struggle to utilise what's on offer. There is documentation which is very technical and certain tabs or sections could do with info buttons to provide some more understanding.

Like a lot of the other data centre sites, there is a lot of inconsistencies when navigating the site, an important one to consider is breadcrumb paths which are usually shown at the top left of the page like in the image below. These should show the path to the current page on the site relative to the parent pages that lead to this page. For example, the breadcrumb path in the image below should be Home > Data > NGDC to indicate that this is the NGDC homepage but it instead implies that this is the Data page.

The **UK Polar Data Centre** is not explicitly defined and sits fairly hidden within the British Antarctic Survey website, I was unable to find the PDC logo anywhere on the site. This suggests a huge amount of content on the site that could easily be simplified or condensed. The complex site topology also reduces navigability and creates inconsistent breadcrumb paths which further complicate the user's

mental model of the site. You can see in the image below a breadcrumb path which references itself. 'Our Data' should also be called 'Data'.

The site has a few bells and whistles like interactive panels and scrolling carousel widgets, however, I found a few of these that didn't function, contained broken links, or broke after interacting with them. There are also multiple search options across the site with extra filtering options that do not function. Filtering by location when searching the staff page is one example and another is on the 'Discovery Metadata System' which searches through available datasets. You can filter the results using the 'Refine List' feature unless you have searched for something in the text box, in which case it will not work.

The NERC Environmental Data Service is a network of data centres that stores and provides access to environmental data from NERC-funded research. Ideally, this should provide clear feedback on the data download status. Additional filter options are missing. API access and bulk download options are features that would improve efficiency. It is also important to check if the metadata are consistent across the different data centres. Some of the terminology is confusing to non-experts. The core goal is to adhere to FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) data principles. This significantly impacts usability, especially for data discovery and reuse.

Common usability issues

Navigation and organisation

I would say the most important aspect of a site's functionality is the ease with which users can navigate to find what they are looking for on the site. This includes intuitive categorisation of pages under relevant parent pages and consistent breadcrumb paths that highlight the user's current location within the site structure.

One of the most effective ways to improve site navigation is to reduce the amount of content held within the site, not only does this minimise the amount of individual pages and thus the choices the user has to make, but it also should reduce the number on total clicks needed to reach a certain page with less child, and grandchild pages to click through.

Lots of the data centre sites have multiple different paths you can take to get to the same page, which some might think helps improve the navigability of the site, however, it actually can add more confusion and complexity to the topology of the site. This combined with inconsistent breadcrumb paths means the user's mental model of the site is distorted and can lead to confusion and frustration when aiming to navigate the site. Simplifying the site structure helps create a clearer mental model of the site for users.

Consistency

Consistent design choices across the site are vital as well as features that are consistent with other sites both in environmental science and in the wider internet. This can be thought of as the collective visual language of the internet - a set of visual cues and conventions that users have come to expect from websites.

This includes things like hyperlinks, icons, tabs, drop-down boxes and more. Most users will be familiar with such features which helps the job of a website designer since they don't need to be explicit about certain things and can instead use 'shortcuts'. However, on numerous occasions through the website review, I found sections that go against what the user would come to expect from specific indicators, such as text or headings that look like hyperlinks but don't link anywhere, or buttons that look like drop-down boxes but actually download files.

A blue information icon that doesn't tell the user about its nearby feature could be very frustrating to a user trying to figure out how to use a system. This is also applicable when looking within the site: if clicking a blue button takes you to another page within the site, you might be surprised when clicking a blue button elsewhere on the site opens an external link in a new tab. Often these types of links are distinguished by icons.

Ensuring that there is consistency both across the site and with the rest of the internet is vital for a smooth user experience.

Broken & Confusing links

I found at least one broken link in every data centre site. Granted, part of this project involved exploring far into these sites and most of the broken links appear in hard-to-find areas of the site, however, some did appear in more prominent places such as the homepage of BODC.

The CoreTrustSeal is a community-based organisation that offers certification to trustworthy data repositories, providing a scheme for assessment against published criteria. All EDS data centres seek to obtain this certification as evidence of operation of trustworthy repositories for the community. Each data centre links to its certification differently; some of these links are especially convoluted and send users down unnecessary rabbit holes.

Distinction between the research centre and the data centre

Something I found for two of the data centres (NGDC & PDC) was a very fuzzy distinction between the NERC research centre and the data centre. I am unsure if this is by design but BGS and BAS have the website for their respective data centre embedded or 'hidden' within their main site. So much so that you often wouldn't even have realised you have crossed over from the research centre to the data centre site. There is no change in theming, logo, or even URL depending on the site.

I think this unclear boundary between the research & data centre relates to a wider discussion about the importance of having our services showcased/promoted. If users weren't already familiar with the data centre they might not gain a clear understanding from the website.

Search Functionality

An important that is relevant for the data centre sites is an effective search functionality. This is because one of the common features that all the data centres should offer is the ability to search through their large catalogue of environmental data. Since these catalogues have such a large variety of data, the ideal search function should have a lot of options for refining the search, such as being able to specify the time series, location, data types, year published etc of the dataset. Disappointingly, however, a lot of the site's search pages don't function in the way you would hope.

Mostly the issues come from the 'refine search' options that filter the search results to more specific categories, often it just doesn't filter the options correctly, or sometimes what it's filtering for isn't fully explained.

This isn't just the case when searching for datasets but also for other search functions on the site like searching for staff members or just searching across the site.

Lessons learnt

In terms of what we learnt conducting these website reviews, the biggest takeaway we have is that the simpler the better! Having an overly complicated website rammed full of content and pages is only going to make the experience of using the site more of a hassle. More content on the site also makes it more likely that stuff falls through the cracks and is forgotten about, leading to broken links and missing pages.

The search is the most important aspect of the sites, alongside providing data management advice, informing people of the research and alerting users to current status updates. Aside from those, most users are just there to find, access and interact with the data. Because of this, being able to find or discover this data is a top priority and thus, a functioning, efficient, and intuitive search engine is vital for every data centre site.

From looking at the sites and comparing them against our own experience, it is clear that there usually isn't anyone who is dedicated to user experience amongst the websites. Based on the CEDA data centre, some people's roles will involve adding and editing new content, and updating the website. However, it is often no one's job to look at the site as a whole to examine how it flows and how the topography affects the user experience. This shows how important it is to dedicate time to do top-down examinations of the site.

Opportunities and future recommendations

Speaking to users directly who access our sites and finding out what they use the site for and how would they improve it. This project was great at giving us a broad overview of all the sites however it was limited as it was carried out by data centre employees who will inherently be biased. Hearing feedback directly from users will give us a fuller picture of the landscapes of our sites.

This also provides an opportunity for different members of the data centres to get together and share ideas, knowledge and suggestions with each other. Since we are generally trying to accomplish similar goals, working collaboratively would have numerous benefits. This should also encourage the data centres to have a big think about the structure of our sites, and how they fit together under the EDS. Would it be better to develop the EDS catalogue and have our individual sites be focused on our specific fields?

It creates opportunities for the creation of new content and services, if we've highlighted things that are missing from our sites or gaps that could be filled, this is a great opportunity to start work towards filling those in. This could be a new content platform, a central place to find information or even tools that help users access data.